

The Influence of Attached Rings on the Formation of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part I.

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It has been shown in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 181) that strong hydrochloric acid converts *o*-phenylenediaryldithiocarbamides into heptathiodiazine derivatives.

In continuation of the same work, some new substituted thiocarbamide derivatives have been prepared with the object of making a comparative study of the ease and nature of their transformation into cyclic structures as conditioned by the presence of one or more phenylene residues.

o-Thiocarbamidobenzoylformic acids (II), prepared by the action of thiocarbamides on *o*-aminobenzoylformic acid gives heptadiazine derivatives (III) on treatment with acetic anhydride.

The alternative formula (III a) has been rejected on the ground that the compound does not suffer any change on being boiled with acetic anhydride or strong hydrochloric acid, though in accordance with the observation of De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 32) a compound of this structure (III a) would have lost the thiocarbamido group. It is soluble in cold dilute alkali and is precipitated unchanged by acids and forms an insoluble lead salt.

Ethylenediaryldithiocarbamides (IV), prepared by the action of two molecules of mustard oil on ethylenediamine remain unchanged even when boiled with strong hydrochloric acid or 15 % caustic potash solution.

1:2-Naphthylenediaryldithiocarbamides (V) in contrast with the ethylenedithiocarbamides, suffer ring-closure readily on being treated with strong hydrochloric acid or 15 % caustic potash solution to yield naphthylenethiocarbamide (VI).

The tendency of the phenanthrene-9:10-dithiocarbamides for ring-closure is so very great that during the process of their formation

from 9:10-diaminophenanthrene and mustard oils, they actually pass into the cyclic thiocarbamide (VIII).

That the solvent pyridine does not exert any ring-closing influence in this reaction has been proved by the fact that 1:2-naphthylenediamine under similar condition yields only 1:2-naphthylenedithiocarbamide (V).

A comparison of the above reactions shows clearly how the phenylene residue plays a very important part in the formation of cyclic structures. Ethylenedithiocarbamide in which there is no phenylene residue, does not give any ring compound; compounds (I a) and (II) contain one phenylene residue and they give heptathiodiazine and heptadiazine derivatives respectively. Naphthylenedithiocarbamide derivative (V) containing two phenylene residues gives the most stable cyclic thiocarbamide. The presence of one more phenylene residue in phenanthrene-9:10-dithiocarbamide (VII) is so very helpful for ring-closure that it cannot even be isolated. The tendency to ring-closure, thus, appears to increase with the increase in the number of phenylene residues.

The cyclic thiocarbamides (VI, VIII) are similar to *o*-phenylene-thiocarbamide prepared by Lellmann (*Annalen*, 1884, 221, 14) in all their properties. *o*-Phenylenethiocarbamide yields only one alkali-insoluble monobenzoyl derivative (IX) though *o*-phenylenecarbamide has been found by Heller and collaborators (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1925, ii, 111, 1) to yield, under varying conditions of experiment, two different benzoyl derivatives viz., *N-N'*-dibenzoyl and mono-oxybenzoyl. It is clear, therefore, that *o*-phenylenethiocarbamide can exist only in the monothiol form.

(IX)

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Phenylthiocarbamidobenzoylformic acid (II, R=Ph).—Phenyl-mustard oil (2.7 g.) was added to an alcoholic solution of the potassium salt of *o*-aminobenzoylformic acid (4 g.) prepared according to the method of Erdmann (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1841, 24, 13) and the solution was boiled under reflux for about 2 hours, cooled and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a white solid separated which crystallised from alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 173-74° (decomp.), yield 4 g. It is soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution. (Found: N, 9.21. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 9.33 per cent).

1-*N*-Phenyl-2-thioketo-4:5-benzo-6:7-diketo-1:3-heptadiazine (III, R=Ph).—The above compound (II, R=Ph) was heated under reflux with excess of acetic anhydride for about an hour. The clear solution was diluted with water and evaporated almost to dryness, when a tarry mass was obtained which was treated with a dilute solution of caustic soda. The alkaline solution on acidification gave a solid which crystallised from acetone in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 155-57°. It is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution. (Found: N, 9.71; S, 11.68. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 9.92; S, 11.34 per cent).

oo-Tolylthiocarbamidobenzoylformic acid (II, R=*o*-tolyl).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound (II, R=Ph). It crystallised from alcohol in colourless

rectangular plates, m.p. 208-10° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.59. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 8.91 per cent).

1-N-o-Tolyl-2-thioketo-4:5-benzo-6:7-diketo-1:3-heptadiazine (III, R=o-tolyl).— The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound (III, R=Ph). It crystallised from acetone in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 205.06°. (Found: S, 11.12. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 10.81 per cent).

op-Tolylthiocarbamidobenzoylformic acid (II, R=p-tolyl) crystallised from alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 165.66° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.64. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 8.91 per cent).

o-Phenylcarbamidobenzoylformic acid.—Phenyl isocyanate (2.4 g.) was added to an alcoholic solution of potassium salt of o-aminobenzoylformic acid (4 g.) and the solution was boiled under reflux for about an hour, cooled and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a white solid came out, the bicarbonate solution of which yielded on acidification a white solid which crystallised from alcohol in beautiful colourless prisms, m.p. 179-80°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 9.71. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.85 per cent). The compound, on treatment with acetic anhydride yielded a tarry product which could not be purified.

Ethylene-sym-diphenyldithiocarbamide (IV, R=Ph) was prepared according to the method of Lellmann and Würthner (*Annalen*, 1885, 228, 234); the action of strong hydrochloric acid or 15% caustic potash solution did not produce any change upon this and other ethylenedithiocarbamides.

Ethylene-sym-di-p-tolyldithiocarbamide (IV, R=p-tolyl).— The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound, yield almost quantitative. The compound crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 194.95°. (Found: N, 15.52. $C_{18}H_{22}N_4S_2$ requires N, 15.64 per cent).

Ethylene-sym-di-o-tolyldithiocarbamide (IV, R=o-tolyl) crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 15.59. $C_{18}H_{22}N_4S_2$ requires N, 15.64 per cent).

Ethylene-sym-diallyldithiocarbamide (IV, R=allyl) crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 103.04°. (Found: N, 21.68. $C_{10}H_{18}N_4S_2$ requires N, 21.70 per cent).

Ethylene-sym-dimethyldithiocarbamide (IV, R=Me).— The method of preparation was the same as before, m.p. 85.86°. (Found: N, 27.35. $C_6H_{14}N_4S_2$ requires N, 27.18 per cent).

1:2-Naphthylenethiocarbamide (VI).—*1:2-Naphthylenediphenyldithiocarbamide* (6.7 g.) prepared according to the method of Schieffelin (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1377), was heated under reflux on the water-bath with 15% caustic potash solution (140 c.c.) for 10 hours. The filtered solution, on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid, yielded a white solid which was dried and carefully weighed, yield 20.5%. It crystallised from pyridine in colourless plates, m.p. above 300°. It is soluble in cold dilute alkali and precipitated by acids. It forms an insoluble lead salt. Like *o*-phenylenethiocarbamide it also cannot be desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury. (Found: N, 14.41; S, 16.14. $C_{11}H_8N_2S$ requires N, 14.0; S, 16.0 per cent). The same compound (VI) was obtained when *1:2-naphthylenediphenyldithiocarbamide* was heated with strong hydrochloric acid under reflux for about an hour.

o-Phenylenediphenyldithiocarbamide (6.7 g.) was similarly heated on the water-bath with 15% caustic potash solution (140 c.c.) for 10 hours. The yield of the thioheptadiazine (I, R=Ph) was 19.5%.

1:2-Naphthylenedi-p-tolyldithiocarbamide (V, R=*p*-tolyl).—An alcoholic solution of *1:2-naphthylenediamine* (1.6 g.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath with *p*-tolylmustard oil (3 g.) for about an hour when a white crystalline precipitate was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. above 300°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: N, 12.01. $C_{26}H_{24}N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.28 per cent). Like the corresponding phenyl compound (V, R=Ph) it also gave *1:2-naphthylenethiocarbamide* (VI) when heated with 15% caustic potash solution or strong hydrochloric acid.

1:2-Naphthylenedixylyldithiocarbamide (V, R=xylyl).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound (V, R=*p*-tolyl), m.p. above 300°. The xylylmustard oil used here has been obtained from *1:3:4*-xylidine. (Found: N, 11.31. $C_{28}H_{28}N_4S_2$ requires N, 11.57 per cent). It also gave *1:2-naphthylenethiocarbamide* with 15% caustic potash solution.

9:10-Phenanthrenethiocarbamide (VIII).—A pyridine solution of *9:10-diaminophenanthrene hydrochloride* (2.8 g.), freshly prepared according to the method of Paschoor (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2738; Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 3684), was heated under reflux with phenylmustard oil (2.7 g.) and the requisite amount of sodium acetate dissolved

in the smallest quantity of water, for about $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour when a crystalline precipitate was obtained which crystallised from pyridine in brownish rectangular plates, m.p. above 300° . It is soluble in cold dilute alkali and precipitated by acids. It gives an insoluble lead salt with lead acetate solution, yield 1.6 g. (Found: N, 11.17; S, 13.14. $C_{15}H_{10}N_2S$ requires N, 11.20; S, 12.80 per cent). From the mother liquor diphenylthiocarbamide was isolated and identified with a genuine sample.

The same compound (VIII) was obtained when a pyridine solution of 9:10-phenanthrenediamine hydrochloride was heated with *p*-tolyl- or *o*-tolylmustard oil.

1-Benzoylthiol-3:4-benzo-2:5-diazole (IX).—The benzoyl derivative was prepared by the usual method and crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. $186-87^{\circ}$. (Found: S, 12.34. $C_{14}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires S, 12.59 per cent). *o*-Phenylenethiocarbamide was dissolved in various proportions of alkali, but in each case the monosodium salt was obtained which yielded the above monobenzoyl derivative (IX).

My thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Guha, D. Sc. for his keen interest in the present investigation.

